

Master's Thesis

**Accurate inner product for
vectors of middle to large
dimension**

by

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Declaration by Candidate

I, KAI TORBEN OHLHUS (student of Computer Science and Engineering at Hamburg University of Technology, matriculation number 20835462), hereby declare that this thesis is my own work and effort and that it has not been submitted anywhere for any award. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged.

Hamburg, 12th December, 2013

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Abstract

The inner product is one of the most elementary algebraic operations and the basis for a large number of numerical applications and computations that are performed using binary floating-point arithmetic on computers. Depending on the condition of the input data, straight forward implementations of the inner product are very inaccurate and of limited use for verified computations. To overcome this issue, many algorithms have been developed in the past with different strengths and weaknesses. This Master's Thesis introduces new algorithms for summation and inner product computation, that make use of the Fused Multiply-Add (FMA) instruction, which will be part of upcoming state of the art computer instruction sets. The proposed algorithms scale well for vector lengths of about 10^3 elements and more.

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List of Abbreviations

AVX

Advanced Vector Extensions.

binary64

IEEE 754-2008 double precision.

C++11

C++ programming language standard ISO/IEC 14882:2011.

C11

C programming language standard ISO/IEC 9899:2011.

CPU

Central Processing Unit.

FLOP

Floating-point Operation.

FMA

Fused Multiply-Add.

FPU

Floating-Point Unit.

GCC

GNU Compiler Collection.

GLIBC

GNU C Library.

IEEE 754-1985

IEEE Standard for Binary Floating-Point Arithmetic (also known as IEC 60559:1989).

IEEE 754-2008

IEEE Standard for Floating-Point Arithmetic.

libstdc++

GNU Standard C++ Library.

MMX

Floating-Point instruction set.

SIMD

Single Instruction Multiple Data.

SSE

Streaming SIMD Extensions.

Introduction

This Master's Thesis deals with the software realization of one of the most elementary algebraic operation, the inner product. The first objective of this thesis is to compute the inner product as accurate as possible without violating the second objective to do it as efficient as possible for middle and large dimension vector lengths. Hereby middle dimension describes vectors with about 10^3 elements and accordingly large dimension vectors with more than 10^6 elements.¹

The inner product is the basis for a large number of numerical applications and computations that are performed using binary floating-point arithmetic on computers. Therefore in Chapter 2 this floating-point arithmetic, specified by the IEEE, is introduced. One part of this specification are the rounding modes, that are examined in detail. Furthermore methods are presented to efficiently extract the exponent part of a binary64. Another part of the IEEE specification is the FMA instruction. This instruction is one of the main reasons for writing this thesis, as it becomes available as hardware realisation for upcoming generations of consumer processors. The FMA instruction itself and the usage from the programming languages C and C++ are analysed comprehensively in Chapter 3.

¹Note that a vector with 10^9 IEEE 754-2008 double precision (binary64) elements would almost completely fill the whole 8 GB of main memory of a state of the art computer system.

Computing accurate inner products is strongly connected to computing accurate sums, which are treated in Chapter 4. In this chapter some previous approaches and basic concepts are presented, followed by the introduction of the new algorithm *BucketSum* for accurate summation. In Chapter 5 many of the summation approaches are advanced in order to compute accurate inner products. Especially *BucketSum* is extended to *BucketDotProd* and *FMAWrapperDotProd*. Both algorithms exploit the features of the FMA instruction. In this chapter it is shown, that other algorithms benefit from the existence of a hardware version of FMA as well. All presented algorithms are therefore tested numerically using a benchmark program for summation and inner products in the corresponding chapters. The test system for the benchmark programs is described in Appendix A. Finally, the results of this thesis are concluded in Chapter 6 with a perspective for the future.

There is a CD attached to this Master's Thesis, which contains a digital version of this thesis, all created software, and selected digital versions of referenced papers. Appendix E lists the detailed content of the CD.

Binary floating-point arithmetic

This chapter is a short introduction to the used notation and important aspects of the binary floating-point arithmetic as defined in the most recent IEEE Standard for Floating-Point Arithmetic (IEEE 754-2008). A more comprehensive introduction, including non-binary floating-point arithmetic, is given in [MBdD⁺10, Chapters 2 and 3].

2.1. Notation and encoding

In this Master's Thesis only the binary, 64 bit floating-point format is regarded. In the floating-point standard it is called binary64. The C and C++ data type *double* realize this format as well. [ISO11a, Annex F.2] [ISO11b, Chapter 18.3.2]. The set of normal and subnormal binary64 floating-point numbers $x \in \mathbb{F}$ is defined by the precision $p = 53$ and the exponent constant $E = 1023$.

$$x = \begin{cases} \pm 1.m_1m_2 \dots m_{p-1} \cdot 2^e, & -E + 1 \leq e \leq E & \text{normal} \\ \pm 0.m_1m_2 \dots m_{p-1} \cdot 2^{-E} & & \text{subnormal} \end{cases}$$

Next to normal and subnormal numbers, a binary64 can take the special values $\pm\infty$ and *NaN* [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 3.2]. For this Master's Thesis the binary64 encoding plays an important role, e.g. for the exponent extraction (see Chapter 2.3). This

encoding is shown in Figure 2.1 with the most significant sign bit, an eleven bit exponent and a 52 bit significant [IEE08, Chapter 3.4].

■ **Figure 2.1.:** Encoding of a binary64 floating-point number.

To get an idea of the range of binary64 numbers, some useful macro constants of the *double* data type from the C standard library header `<float.h>` [ISO11a, Chapter 5.2.4.2.2] are listed in Table 2.1.

Marco name	Value	Description
DBL_MIN	2^{-1022}	Smallest positive normal number
DBL_TRUE_MIN	2^{-1074}	Smalles positive subnormal number
DBL_MAX	$0x1.fffffffffffff \cdot 2^{1023}$	Largest positive normal number
DBL_EPSILON	2^{-52}	Relative unit roundoff

■ **Table 2.1.:** Some *double* macro constants from `<float.h>`.

2.2. Rounding

IEEE 754-2008 requires the results of conforming floating-point operations to be correctly rounded [IEE08, Definition 2.1.12 and Chapter 9]. The following description is a brief summary of [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 2.2] to explain a correctly rounded floating-point number in the context of a given rounding mode. Assume a general positive, normalized, binary, infinite precise floating-point number $y \in \mathbb{R}$. Then the first p bits are the representable bits (remember for binary64 the precision p is 53), followed by a rounding bit and the remaining bits results in the sticky bit. The sticky bit is set, if any bit of $m_{p+1}m_{p+2} \dots$ is set.

$$y = 1.\underbrace{m_1m_2 \dots m_{p-1}}_{\text{representable bits}} \underbrace{m_p}_{\text{round bit}} \underbrace{m_{p+1}m_{p+2} \dots}_{\text{sticky bit}} \cdot 2^e, \quad -\infty < e < \infty$$

In order to be representable as binary64, y has to be rounded to a floating-point number $x \in \mathbb{F}$. This rounding operation will be defined by the function $x = fl(y)$. The result

of $fl()$ is dependent on the active rounding mode. The IEEE 754-2008 specifies the following rounding modes:

- `roundToNearest`
 - ◆ `roundTiesToEven`
 - ◆ `roundTiesToAway`
- `roundTowardPositive`
- `roundTowardNegative`
- `roundTowardZero`

For a binary IEEE 754-2008 implementation *roundTiesToEven* is the default rounding mode, though the other three rounding modes have to be implemented as well [IEE08, Chapter 4.3.3]. Depending on the sign of y , *roundTowardZero* behaves like *roundTowardPositive* or *roundTowardNegative* respectively. This rounding mode will be neglected in the following examinations. Table 2.2 (according to [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 2.2.1]) gives an overview how the different rounding modes work. "-" indicates that the significant of y is simply truncated after m_{p-1} . "+" means that 2^{-p+1} has to be added to the significant, that is truncated after bit m_{p-1} .

round bit	sticky bit	roundTowardNegative	roundTowardPositive	roundTiesToEven
0	0	-	-	-
0	1	-	+	-
1	0	-	+	-
1	1	-	+	+

■ **Table 2.2.:** Comparison of rounding modes.

Thus an infinite precise result of an arithmetic operation y is correctly rounded according to a rounding mode, if the rules above are applied. This definition is intangible for mathematical proofs on error estimations of floating-point operations. To overcome this problem, several measures have been introduced. The first one is the relative unit roundoff ϵ , especially for binary64 holds $\epsilon = DBL_EPSILON$. With

this measure a correctly rounded result $x = fl(y)$ according to [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 2.2.3] can be defined as:

$$\frac{|y - x|}{|y|} \begin{cases} \leq \frac{1}{2}\epsilon & , \text{ for roundToNearest} \\ < \epsilon & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This more intuitive measure for the term correctly rounded means, that for any rounding mode the relative error should be smaller than the representable bits of the rounded floating-point result x . Additionally for roundToNearest the relative error can be maximal exactly the tie value $0.5 \cdot \epsilon$ (the round bit of y), or is "one bit smaller" than for any other rounding mode.

A measure for the absolute error is the "unit in the last place" $ulp(y)$, $y \in \mathbb{R}$, which is defined for any real number in [MBdD⁺10, Definition 5] as:

$$ulp(y) = \max(2^{e-p+1}, DBL_TRUE_MIN) \quad y \in [2^e, 2^{e+1})$$

ϵ and $ulp(y)$ are related via $ulp(1) = \epsilon$ [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 2.6.4]. Roughly spoken, $ulp(x)$, $x \in \mathbb{F}$ is the significance of bit m_{p-1} of x or reciting the original definition:

" $ulp(x)$ is the gap between the two floating-point numbers nearest to x , even if x is one of them." [MBdD⁺10, Page 32]

When there is a "unit in the last place", it seems likely that there exists a "unit in the first place" as well. And indeed, Rump, Ogita and Oishi introduce $ufp(y)$ in [ROO08, Chapter 2]:

$$ufp(y) = \begin{cases} 2^{\lceil \log_2 |y| \rceil} & , \text{ for } y \in \mathbb{R} \setminus 0 \\ 0 & , \text{ for } y = 0 \end{cases}$$

Both ϵ and $ulp(y)$ are often found in literature about error analysis of floating-point algorithms in various forms and have some weaknesses in their informative value. Discussions about the limitations can be found in [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 2] and with emphasis on $ufp(y)$ in [Rum11].

2.3. Fast exponent extraction

A crucial operation for the later proposed algorithms is to extract the exponent of a binary64. The standard C library offers two functions to extract the exponent part, namely *frexp()* [ISO11a, Chapter 7.12.6.4] [ISO11b, Chapter 26.8] and *ilogb()* [ISO11a, Chapter 7.12.6.5] [ISO11b, Chapter 26.8]. Additionally two more hardware dependent methods were tested too. The first of these is to define a data structure, that allows to conveniently view certain bit positions of a binary64 as unsigned integers, see Listing 2.1. This approach has also been chosen for the algorithm implementations in [ZH10]. As done in line 12 of Listing 2.1, the binary64 has to be cast to the structure in order to extract the exponent. This approach is called "bit ops" in Figure 2.2 as it performs operations on the bit level representation of the binary64.

```

1  typedef struct
2  {
3      unsigned mantissa_low:32;
4      unsigned mantissa_high:20;
5      unsigned exponent:11;
6      unsigned sign:1;
7  } ieee754_double;
8
9  /* ... */
10
11 double d = 1.0;
12 unsigned exponent = ((ieee754_double *) &d)->exponent;

```

■ **Listing 2.1:** Exponent extraction via type conversion.

The last considered approach is to use inline assembly to directly call the assembler instruction *fxtract* wrapped by a function with an interface similar to that one of *frexp()*, see Listing 2.2.

```

1  inline double
2  asm_fxtract (const double input, int *exponent)
3  {
4      double result = 0.0;
5      double exp = 0.0;
6      __asm__ ("fxtract": "=t" (result), "=u" (exp):"0" (input));
7      *exponent = (int) exp;
8      return result;
9  }

```

■ **Listing 2.2:** Exponent extraction via inline assembly.

To compare these four approaches for extracting the exponent of a binary64, a small benchmark program has been created. The benchmark program performs the extraction operation on a varying number of input operands and repeats for each number of operands the action 100 times. This has been done to receive measurable results, as this operation is performed too fast to obtain reliable results for a small amount of input. The timings of the four methods have been compared relative to the time needed by a simple addition operation on the same amount of input data, as visible in Figure 2.2. The choice of the addition operation as reference value is not deciding. Figure 2.2 reveals almost equal timings for the multiplication operation. Because of this, the multiplication plot is hidden behind the addition plot in Figure 2.2. A final remark on the benchmark program is the instruction-level parallelism. The benchmark was performed with one to four parallel instructions by a technique called "partial loop unrolling", which is explained later in Chapter 3.4.

Figure 2.2 shows, that type casting ("bit ops") performs best for extracting the exponent and might have been chosen intentionally for the algorithm implementations in [ZH10]. Even for the parallel case this approach doesn't perform worse than an addition or multiplication operation, what is beneficial if one is able to parallelise this task for the input data. One drawback of this approach is, that like the assembler instruction *fxtract*, it is hardware depended. Thus a user of the presented algorithms has to take care for the data structure of Listing 2.1 to be applicable to his machine. If the user favours generality over performance, the standard library function *frexp()* should be chosen for the task of exponent extraction.

2.3. FAST EXPONENT EXTRACTION

■ **Figure 2.2.:** Exponent extraction performance compared to the add operation.

2. BINARY FLOATING-POINT ARITHMETIC

The Fused-Multiply-Add operation

IEEE 754-2008 standardizes the new operation FMA [IEE08, Page 4]. This operation will be supported by hardware in upcoming Central Processing Unit (CPU) instruction sets from AMD¹ [Hol12, Page 3] and Intel² [Meg13, Page 4], which at the time of writing are two market leading CPU manufactures. What makes this instruction so attractive is, that it performs two floating-point operations in a single step³, which can be beneficial for speeding up algorithms. A short history excerpt and a very comprehensive analysis of various algorithms using the FMA operation can be found in [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 5].

3.1. Specification

This section deals with how FMA is specified by IEEE 754-2008. Quoting the standard:

"The operation *fusedMultiplyAdd*(x, y, z) computes $(x \cdot y) + z$ as if with unbounded range and precision, rounding only once to the destination format." [IEE08, Definition 2.1.28]

¹Advanced Micro Devices, Inc.

²Intel Corporation

³This does not necessarily mean a single CPU clock cycle.

3. THE FUSED-MULTIPLY-ADD OPERATION

Algorithm 1 Fused-Multiply-Add (FMA)

```
1: function FMA( $a, b, c$ )
2:   return  $fl((a \cdot b) + c)$ 
3: end function
```

The property, that the result of the FMA operation is only rounded once in the end, is very important. First of all, one is able to write algorithms that can rely on this property of no intermediate rounding like it would happen if $(x \cdot y) + z$ is evaluated by two floating-point operations. But on the other hand the programmer has to take care for compiler optimizations. For example an expression like $a \cdot b + x \cdot y$ might be contracted to $FMA(a, b, x \cdot y)$ and any assumptions about intermediate rounding are falsified [MBdD⁺10, Page 214]. More on the compiler settings for correct usage for FMA follows in Chapter 3.3.

3.2. Hardware realization

At the time of writing this thesis the FMA operation is not a fully adopted by all common used computer architectures. Thus, it is important to check if the used system uses a hardware implemented FMA operation in order to avoid slow software emulations as the C programming language standard ISO/IEC 9899:2011 (C11) standard remarks [ISO11a, Chapter 7.12].

Since the year 1990 the FMA instruction has been supported by several processors, like the *HP/Intel Itanium*, which has been used as testing system by many algorithm implementors in the past [MBdD⁺10, Page 151]. For examples see [ORO05, Page 8] and [GLL07]. These processors are mainly used for scientific or business applications, but the focus of this thesis are more common used processor architectures like the Intel 64 and AMD64⁴ architectures, which are mainly compatible with each other. AMD assures that "[...] floating-point operations comply with the IEEE-754 standard." [AMD13a, Chapter 1.1.5], as Intel does for FMA too [Int13a, Chapter 14.5.1]. So it is assumed for this thesis, that there is no violation of IEEE 754-2008 on hardware level.

⁴Also known as AMD x86-64.

Sign	79	63	0	
Exponent	Significand / MMX0			R0
Exponent	Significand / MMX1			R1
Exponent	Significand / MMX2			R2
Exponent	Significand / MMX3			R3
Exponent	Significand / MMX4			R4
Exponent	Significand / MMX5			R5
Exponent	Significand / MMX6			R6
Exponent	Significand / MMX7			R7

■ **Figure 3.1.:** x87 FPU and mapped MMX registers.

■ **Figure 3.2.:** AVX packed double addition *VADDPD ymm1, ymm2, ymm3/m256*.

For analyzing the FMA operation on hardware level, a deeper understanding of the floating-point instruction sets and used registers is required. With this knowledge one can later check on the assembly level, if the "real" FMA is used. Many currently available and all upcoming Intel 64 and AMD64 CPUs support four floating-point instruction sets:

- **x87 Floating-Point Unit (FPU):** This instruction set is designed for scalar IEEE Standard for Binary Floating-Point Arithmetic (also known as IEC 60559:1989) (IEEE 754-1985) floating-point operations on eight separate 80 bit FPU data registers. These registers are used as a stack, to avoid long opcodes. The mnemonics are prefixed by an "F" (float), for example *FADD ST(0),ST(i)* is such an

3. THE FUSED-MULTIPLY-ADD OPERATION

instruction. $ST(x)$ is the stack pointer to some FPU data register x . The shown instruction replaces $ST(0)$ with $ST(0) + ST(i)$. An urgent problem with these instructions arises from the 80 bit long registers and when, due to execution optimization, floating-point operands are kept in the registers for more than one operation. This problem of "double rounding" is described in [MBdD⁺10, Chapters 3.3.1]. For more information about the x87 FPU, see [Int13a, Chapter 8] and [AMD13a, Chapter 6]).

- **Floating-Point instruction set (MMX) and 3DNow!**⁵: In contrast to the x87 FPU instruction set, this one is intended for Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) operations. Intel supports only integer data types, whereas AMD introduced the extension *3DNow!* for supporting floating-point data types as well. This instruction set makes use of eight 64 bit MMX data registers that are mapped onto the FPU data registers (see Figure 3.1). So instead of having two scalar operands for an instruction, MMX allows to operate on so called packed values, which are vectors of some data type (see Figure 3.2). For AMD only, the mnemonics are prefixed with "PF" (packed float), for example *PFADD mmx1, mmx2/mem64* would add the packed values from two MMX data registers and store the results in the first operand register. Due to the 64 bit limitation, only two packed single precision floating-point types could be used (see [AMD13d, Page 94] for more details). [Int13a, Chapter 9] [AMD13a, Chapter 5]
- **Legacy Streaming SIMD Extensions (SSE)**⁶: To legacy SSE belong SSE1, SSE2, SSE3, SSSE3, SSE4, SSE4.1, SSE4.2 and SSE4A. All these instruction sets are subsequent extensions with new instructions. The difference to MMX is that SSE instructions can operate on both MMX (thus FPU) data registers and eight to sixteen 128 bit *XMM* data registers depending on enabled 64 bit mode. The packed value concept stays the same as in MMX, but offers more operands at the same time and the support of floating-point types. An example for adding two packed double precision floating-point types is *ADDPD xmm1, xmm2/mem128*, like with *PFADD* the result is stored in the first operand register [AMD13c, Page 19]. The instruction suffix "SD" thus indicates a scalar double-

⁵Instruction set introduced by AMD.

⁶Terms "legacy SSE" and "extended SSE" are adopted from [AMD13a, Chapter 4.1.2] for this thesis.

precision operation and the suffix "PD" a packed double operation. [Int13a, Chapter 10-12] [AMD13a, Chapter 4]).

- Extended SSE:** This instruction set is the most interesting one for this thesis, as it will include the FMA operation. To extended SSE belongs the Advanced Vector Extensions (AVX) instruction set, that offers 256 bit versions of all legacy SSE instructions and further extensions, that are manufacturer depended and not relevant for this thesis. Sixteen 256 bit *YMM* data registers, whose 128 lower bits are used as *XMM* data registers (see Figure 3.3) are required to perform these extended operations. The mnemonics are prefixed by "V" (VEX-prefix) [Int13a, Chapter 14.1.3]. There is one important difference between Intel and AMD. Both will have support for the so called FMA3 operation, but only AMD will support the FMA4 operation. For the double precision data type FMA3 will be realized in three versions whose mnemonics are *VFMADD132PD*, *VFMADD213PD* and *VFMADD231PD*. The numbers 1, 2 and 3 indicate which registers will be multiplied and added [Lom11, Page 5]. The hardware realized FMA3 operation finally looks for example like this: *VFMADD132PD ymm0, ymm1, ymm2/m256*. The computation performed is $ymm0 = (ymm0 \cdot ymm2) + ymm1$. AMDs FMA4 has the form *VFMADDPD ymm1, ymm2, ymm3, ymm4/mem256*. This operation is non-destructive, that means, that no operand will be overwritten and remain available for further operations. $ymm1 = (ymm2 \cdot ymm3) + ymm4$. [Int13a, Chapter 14] [AMD13c, Chapter 1]

At the time of writing AMD64 already offers the FMA3 operation in processors based upon the microarchitectures "Bulldozer" and "Piledriver". The latter one supports the FMA4 operation as well [Hol12, Page 2]. The AVX instruction set, including FMA3, will be part of Intels fourth generation CoreTM processors with the code name "Haswell" [Meg13, Page 1,4].

With this background of floating-point instruction sets it is possible to determine the availability of FMA on a specific system. The *CPUID* operation is very helpful to get information about AMD or Intel processors. Calling *CPUID* returns a bit pattern that contains all information about the CPU features. The meanings of the individual bits are described in [AMD13b, Appendix E] for AMD or for Intel in [Int13b, Page 219-246]. Additionally Intel provides an assembler pseudo code [Int13a, Chapter

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255	128	0
	XMM0	YMM0
	XMM1	YMM1
	XMM2	YMM2
	XMM3	YMM3
	XMM4	YMM4
	XMM5	YMM5
	XMM6	YMM6
	XMM7	YMM7
	XMM8	YMM8
	XMM9	YMM9
	XMM10	YMM10
	XMM11	YMM11
	XMM12	YMM12
	XMM13	YMM13
	XMM14	YMM14
	XMM15	YMM15

■ **Figure 3.3.:** SSE registers.

14.5.3] to check the availability of FMA. A system test program "SystemProperties" (see Appendix E), attached to this thesis, contains a modified version of that assembler code.

3.3. Software and compiler support

The compiler used in this Master's Thesis is the GNU Compiler Collection (GCC)⁷ (version 4.8.1), a free software compiler, and its C++ front end G++. As the manual suggest, the compiler names GCC and G++ can be used interchangeably for C++ source file input [Sta13, Chapter 1]. GCC links C programs against the GNU C Library

⁷<http://gcc.gnu.org/>

(GLIBC)^{8 9} (version 2.17) [Sta13, Chapter 3.17.13] and C++ programs are linked against the GNU Standard C++ Library (libstdc++)¹⁰. Using GCC guarantees easy reproducibility of this work. It follows a discussion which options have to be passed to the GCC compiler to fulfill the following three properties:

- compliance with the standards C11 or C++ programming language standard ISO/IEC 14882:2011 (C++11) and IEEE 754-2008
- optimized code
- enabling the FMA operation by hardware

To fulfil the first property GCC offers the options `-std=c11` or `-std=c++11` respectively and `-pedantic` [Sta13, Chapter 2]. But GCC is not fully compliant to IEEE 754-2008, C11, and C++11, as online documents state^{11 12} [MBdD⁺10, Page 79]. As long as this issue hasn't been fixed, it is up to the programmer to carefully check the IEEE 754-2008 conformance. The first case where one gets in touch with the broken implementation is the contracted expression, described earlier for FMA. The C11 standard allows to control the usage of these expression with the `FP_CONTRACT` pragma [ISO11a, Chapter 7.12.2] [IEE08, Annex F.6]. According to the GCC manual this pragma is currently not implemented. But contracting expressions is only enabled, if the `-funsafe-math-optimizations` or `-ffast-math` options are used [Sta13, Chapter 4.6]. There are two other switches to archive standard compliance. The first one is `-fexcess-precision=standard` ensuring that "double rounding" (see section 3.2) cannot occur as all casts and assignments are rounded to their semantic type, regardless of being stored in for example an 80 bit register. This option is enabled by default, if `-std` is used. The last one is `-frounding-math` that disables the optimization assumption of the default rounding mode. Doing this, the currently active rounding mode is respected. One drawback is, that `-frounding-math` is marked as experimental for the current version [Sta13, Chapter 3.10].

When optimizing software, there is a trade-off between universality, means that the resulting binaries run on a wide range of architectures and machines, and the best

⁸<https://www.gnu.org/software/libc/>

⁹Note that Ubuntu 13.10 uses <http://www.eglibc.org/>, which is based upon GLIBC.

¹⁰<http://gcc.gnu.org/libstdc++/>

¹¹<http://gcc.gnu.org/c99status.html>

¹²<http://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/libstdc++/manual/status.html>

possible optimization for one specific machine. As in this work the new FMA operation should be used, all optimization decisions are made to primarily work best on the used test system (see Appendix A). Now that the second and third properties are more hardware depended, they can be examined together. GCC offers the option `-O` which allows to generically enable four levels of optimization (0-3). The GCC manual states, that even the highest optimization level `-O3` does not invoke any options that are in conflict with the first targeted property of standard compliance [Sta13, Chapter 3.10]. Thus it is possible to use `-O3` safely. GCC also offers many options to enable or disable machine specific features and operations. To overcome the big effort of checking all feature options for applicability, there is the option `-march=native` that detects all available features of the local machine and enables the feature options accordingly [Sta13, Chapter 3.17.16]. The for this thesis used machine is recognized as `"bdver2"` for example. Because of this the FMA options `-mfma` and `-mfma4` are enabled too. This fulfills the third desired target. All performed optimizations by the compiler can be inspected using the option `-fopt-info` to ensure no undesired optimizations were applied [Sta13, Chapter 3.10].

Checking the processor feature bits, like it was done in Chapter 3.2, only gives the information, that FMA is available on a system. It does not guarantee, that the compiled program makes use of that operation by hardware. To prove the latter, two steps are suggested. The first one is to prove the specified property of single rounding is held. The second one is to inspect the compiled assembler code to find the FMA instruction. A test case for the single rounding property is given in Figure B.1 and Figure B.2. This test case considers any rounding mode. An excerpt of the implementation of Figure B.1 for $exp_a = exp_b = 0$ is given in Listing B.1. These test case programs could verify, that only the hardware FMA instruction results in the "result with FMA" from Figure B.1 and Figure B.2.

A very short excerpt of the compiled program from Listing B.1 for *roundToward-Negative* is given in Listing B.2. Indeed, the FMA4 operation (`vfmaddsd`) and an instance of the FMA3 operation (`vfmadd231sd`) are used in the form of a scalar double-precision operation, because of the "sd" suffix [AMD13c, Page 544-552]. Even if compiled with the highest optimization level `-O3`, it is not possible to use packed double-precision operations, due to data dependencies in the program of

Listing B.1. But for this test program this circumstance is of minor interest.

3.4. Performance

With being able to use the FMA operation it is now interesting to compare the performance to other basic operations. The benchmark program simply repeats an operation on a given amount of data. To be more precise, an outer loop increases the number of repetitions, in this case ten steps from 10^9 to 10^{10} repetitions. This is done to see how the operation scales compared to others. The most important excerpts of the benchmark program are in Listing C.1. A look in the compiled routines (Listings C.2, C.3 and C.4) reveals, that the repeated floating-point operation is performed in a scalar and serial way, indicated by the "sd" suffix, like described in Chapter 3.2. Additionally the code parallelization by a technique called "partial loop unrolling" [AMD12, Chapters 3.4 and 8.2] is taken into account by the benchmark program. Basically this technique means nothing more than to repeat the code for a distinct and independent memory location, e.g. $var[i]$ and $var[i + 1]$. Independent means, that $var[i]$ is not computed from $var[i + 1]$ in a preceding floating-point operation. Partial loop unrolling violates the well-known *Don't Repeat Yourself* design principle, but it allows the compiler to make relaxed assumptions about instruction reordering and register usage. This allows to perform more floating-point operations per clock cycle, thus the instruction-level parallelism increases [AMD12, Chapters 3.4 and 8.2]. The compiled version of the parallelized benchmark program is shown in Listing C.5. A further step would be to make use of packed value ("pd") operations, but later in the proposed algorithms these instructions cannot be used, due to data dependencies and thus it is not considered in the benchmark program. The results of the benchmark program for five levels of parallelism are shown in Figure 3.4.

The results of this benchmark program verify, that the pure FMA operation is as fast as a simple addition and multiplication for AMD "Piledriver" CPUs. The same result was taken by another benchmark as well [Fog13, Page 60]. The reason for the equal results is the usage of the same floating-point multiply/add subunit for all of these operations [Fog13, Pages 49 and 60]. Thus FMA can be used as a hardware implemented operation without having any performance penalties.

3. THE FUSED-MULTIPLY-ADD OPERATION

■ **Figure 3.4.:** FMA performance compared to addition and multiplication.

Accurate summation

Accurate summation of two or more addends in floating-point arithmetic is not a trivial task. It has become an active field of research since the introduction of computers using floating-point arithmetic and resulted in many different approaches, that should only be sketched in Chapter 4.1. The accurate computation of sums is not only the basis for the chapter about accurate inner products, it is also important for residual iterations, geometrical predicates, computer algebra, linear programming or multiple precision arithmetic in general, as it is motivated in [Rum09, Chapter 1].

4.1. Previous work

4.1.1. Presorting the addends

One of the easiest summation algorithms is the Recursive summation (Algorithm 2). Higham describes in [Hig02, Chapter 4] that for this simple algorithm the order of the addends has a huge impact on the accuracy of the resulting sum. The problem with presorting the data is, that even fast sorting algorithms have a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ and in many applications there is no information about the addends in advance available. But the analysing techniques and results from [Hig02, Chapter 4] can be applied later for other algorithms. Additional tools for error analysis are given in [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 6.1.2]. For the purpose of error analysis Higham introduces a condition number $R_{\text{summation}}$ for the addends:

$$R_{\text{summation}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |x_i|}{\left| \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \right|} \quad (4.1)$$

Algorithm 2 Recursive summation.

```
1: function RECURSIVESUMMATION(data, N)
2:   s = 0
3:   for i = 1 to N do
4:     s ← s + datai
5:   end for
6:   return s
7: end function
```

If all addends have the same sign, then $R_{\text{summation}} = 1$. In this case an increasing ordering is suggested. When the numbers of largest magnitude are summed up first, all smaller addends will not influence the final result, even if all small addends together would have a sufficient large magnitude to contribute to the final result as well. If the signs of the largest addends differ, then $R_{\text{summation}} \rightarrow \infty$ and heavy cancellation happens by computing $\sum_{i=1}^N x_i$. Such kind of summation data is called *ill-conditioned* analogue to [Hig02, Chapter 4] and has often the exact result zero. For this kind of addends Higham suggest a decreasing pre ordering.

4.1.2. Error-free transformation and distillation

The most basic error-free summation algorithms transform two input addends, e.g. a and b , into a floating-point sum x and a floating-point approximation error y . These algorithms are called *error-free transformations* [ORO05, Chapter 1.1], if the following is satisfied:

$$a + b = x + y \quad \text{and} \quad x = fl(a + b)$$

It is easy to see, that if $a, b \in \mathbb{F}$ is given, $x, y \in \mathbb{F}$ is valid too. The two most distinct instances fulfilling the error-free transformation property are *FastTwoSum* (Algorithm 3) by Dekker [ORO05, Page 2] and *TwoSum* (Algorithm 4) by Knuth [ORO05, Page

7]. *FastTwoSum* requires three and *TwoSum* six Floating-point Operations (FLOPs). *FastTwoSum* additionally requires $|a| \geq |b|$ and thus unavoidably an expensive branch. So one has to check for the individual use case whether three additional FLOPs exceed the cost of a branch [ORO05, Chapters 1 and 3] [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 4.3]. There exists another algorithm by Priest, which will not be taken into account in this thesis. It requires $|a| \geq |b|$, thus a branch, and more FLOPs than the two already presented algorithms [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 4.3.3].

Algorithm 3 Error-free transformation *FastTwoSum*.

```

1: function FASTTWO SUM( $a, b$ )
2:    $x \leftarrow fl(a + b)$ 
3:    $y \leftarrow fl(fl(a - x) + b)$ 
4:   return ( $x, y$ )
5: end function

```

Algorithm 4 Error-free transformation *TwoSum*.

```

1: function TWOSUM( $a, b$ )
2:    $x \leftarrow fl(a + b)$ 
3:    $z \leftarrow fl(x - a)$ 
4:    $y \leftarrow fl(fl(a - fl(x - z)) + fl(b - z))$ 
5:   return ( $x, y$ )
6: end function

```

The extension of error-free transformations from 2 to N addends is called *distillation* [ORO05, Chapter 1.1].

$$\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^N x_i$$

Distillation means, that in each distillation step k the values of the N individual addends may change, but not their sum. The goal of distillation algorithms is, that after a finite number of steps, assume k steps, $x_n^{(k)}$ approximates $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i$ [Hig02, Chapter 4.4]. The Error-free transformation and distillation properties are preliminaries for cascaded and compensated summation.

4.1.3. Cascaded and compensated summation

If *FastTwoSum* (Algorithm 3) or *TwoSum* (Algorithm 4) is successively applied to all elements of a vector of addends, it is called *cascaded summation*. When each new addend gets corrected by the previously computed error of *FastTwoSum* (like in line 5 Algorithm 5), it is called *compensated summation*. The notation with explicit usage of *FastTwoSum* has been introduced in [MBdD⁺10, Algorithm 6.7]. Algorithm 5 relies on sorted input data $|x_i| \geq |x_{i+1}|$, because of the internal usage of *FastTwoSum*.

Algorithm 5 Kahan's cascaded and compensated summation.

Input: x array of sorted addends

Input: N number of addends in x

Output: s computed sum

```
1: function KAHANSCOMPENSATEDSUMMATION( $x, N$ )
2:    $s \leftarrow x_1$ 
3:    $e \leftarrow 0$ 
4:   for  $i = 2$  to  $N$  do
5:      $y \leftarrow fl(x_i + e)$  ▷ compensation step
6:      $(s, e) \leftarrow FastTwoSum(s, y)$ 
7:   end for
8:   return  $s$ 
9: end function
```

Rump, Ogita and Oishi present in [ORO05] another interesting algorithm, namely *SumK*, which repeats the distillation $k - 1$ times, followed by a final recursive summation. The authors have shown that after the $(k - 1)$ -th repetition of the cascaded summation, the result has improved, as if it has been computed with k -fold working precision.

4.1.4. Long and cascaded accumulators

A completely different approach is not to look for ways to cope with the errors of floating-point arithmetic, instead to change the precision on hardware level. Therefore Kulisch and Miranker proposed the usage of a long high-precision accumulator on hardware level [KM86]. This approach has not been realized so far by common hardware vendors. In his book [Kul13, Chapter 8] Kulisch describes comprehensibly the realization of *Scalar product computation units (SPU)* for common 32 and 64 bit PC

architectures or as coprocessors. Kulisch reports about two more or less successful attempts of coprocessor realizations, the most recent one with a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) [Kul13, Chapter 8.9.3]. The major issue is the time penalty of the much slower FPGA clock rates. But as there is much improvement on that field of research and with intelligent usage of parallelism, it might be possible to create a SPU, that is comparable to nowadays CPU floating-point units. Nevertheless the idea of the long accumulator resulted in a C++ toolbox called C-XSC¹, that is currently maintained by the University of Wuppertal. The C-XSC toolbox has been developed for several years and is thoroughly tested, therefore its version 2.5.3 will be used as reference for checking the correctness of the computed results later in Chapter 4.3.

Another interesting approach came up in a paper by Malcom [Mal71], who caught up Wolfes idea of cascaded accumulators. Malcom modified this idea by splitting each addend in order to add each split part to an appropriate accumulator. Finally all accumulators are summed up in decreasing order of magnitude using ordinary recursive summation. This case was treated in Chapter 4.1.1 and results in a small relative error [Hig02, Chapter 4.4].

4.1.5. Hybrid techniques

Zhu and Hayes published the accurate summation algorithm *OnlineExactSum* [ZH10, Figure 1]. This algorithm claims to be independent of the number of addends and the condition number (see Equation 4.1) of the input. Furthermore the results of *OnlineExactSum* are correctly rounded. *OnlineExactSum* has a constant memory footprint, as it uses a fixed number of cascaded accumulators. Each addends exponent is examined for the choice of an appropriate accumulator and the accumulation is done by Dekkers error-free transformation algorithm *FastTwoSum*. In contrast to Malcoms approach, the final sum up of the cascaded accumulators is done by *iFastSum* [ZH09, Figure 2.2], a distillation algorithm like *SumK*. In their paper [ZH10] Zhu and Hayes proof the correctness of their algorithm by showing, that no accumulator loses any significant digits, and by the correctly rounded result of *iFastSum* for the final sum up. With various run time test for several types of input data they verified the stable and predictable behaviour of *OnlineExactSum*. With this survey on previous work, a

¹http://www2.math.uni-wuppertal.de/wrswt/xsc/cxsc_new.html

new algorithm will be proposed in the following chapter. Many ideas for the proposed algorithm accrued from this previous work and are extended by this new approach.

4.2. BucketSum

4.2.1. Generic description

The proposed algorithm *BucketSum* performs basically two steps, which will be explained comprehensively in this chapter:

1. **Sort and accumulate:** N addends are sorted by magnitude and stored into M buckets, $N \gg M$. All significant bits are preserved.
2. **Summing up buckets:** compute an accurate sum of the M buckets.

This approach is already known from Zhu and Hayes algorithm *HybridSum* [ZH09, Algorithm 2] and from Malcolm [Mal71]. Instead of increasing the precision of the accumulators, the input data is split and stored in several shorter accumulators. So each binary64 number can be seen as an extended-precision accumulator for the reduced input data precision. Like in *HybridSum* [ZH09, Algorithm 2] an array of binary64 numbers is created, each for accumulating a certain part of the full binary64 exponent range. Each element of that array will be called "bucket" in this chapter. For getting an overall picture, the algorithms for the steps 1 and 2 are presented first. The algorithm for step 2 is a slight modification of Kahan's cascaded and compensated summation (Algorithm 5). The compensation step has been taken out of the for-loop to reduce the data dependency. In this modified version (Algorithm 6) all summation errors are accumulated inside the for-loop for the final compensation step. Additionally an initial value for the resulting sum has been introduced.

BucketSum is responsible for step 1 and presented in Algorithm 7. What distinguishes *BucketSum* from *OnlineExactSum* is the ternary partitioning of each floating-point accumulator (bucket). This partitioning is done in order to archive a certain cascaded, overlapping pattern for the accurate summation, as Figure 4.3 shows. The "distance" between two neighbouring buckets is called *shift* and identical to the length $part_2$ in the partitioning. From Figure 4.1 one can see, that the whole generic partitioning pattern consists of the following parts, that are determined in Theorem 2:

Algorithm 6 Modified Kahan’s cascaded and compensated summation.

Input: s initial sum value

Input: x array of sorted addends

Input: N number of addends in x

Output: s computed sum

```

1: function MODIFIEDKAHANSUM( $s, x, N$ )
2:    $err \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
4:      $(s, e) \leftarrow FastTwoSum(s, x_i)$ 
5:      $err \leftarrow fl(err + e)$ 
6:   end for
7:    $s \leftarrow fl(s + err)$  ▷ compensation step
8:   return  $s$ 
9: end function

```

■ **Figure 4.1.:** Generic significant partition.

- **Two set bits** in the beginning.
- **Accumulation reserve** ($part_1$): This length decides about the number of addends, that can be accumulated into a bucket, without losing any significant bits.
- **Variable extension** ($guard$): $guard$ is a variable extension of the following $part_2$.
- **Accumulated exponent range** ($part_2$): Each bucket is assigned to accumulate addends of a certain exponent sub range. $part_2$ is the length of this range. Therefore, $part_2$ is at least one, otherwise no addend may be added to this bucket.
- **Residual** ($part_3$): $part_3$ is only used to preserve significant bits of an addend.

Another characteristic of *BucketSum* is, that there is no fixed splitting of the input addends like in *HybridSum* ([ZH09, Algorithm 2]). The splitting is performed dynamically by *FastTwoSum* as one can see in Algorithm 7 line 9. After giving an overview of *BucketSum*, there follows a more detailed description of the algorithm, which starts with a formal analysis of the bucket partitioning.

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Algorithm 7 BucketSum.

Input: N , number of addends

Input: x , array of N floating-point addends

Output: s , correctly rounded sum $\sum_{i=1}^N x_i$

```

1: function BUCKETSUM( $x, N$ )
2:            $\triangleright a_1$  and  $a_2$  are underflow and  $a_{M-1}$  and  $a_M$  are overflow buckets
3:   create arrays of  $M$  buckets  $a$             $\triangleright a_{2\dots M-2}$  cover SHIFT exponents
4:   create arrays of  $M$  bucket masks  $mask$     $\triangleright mask_1$  is set to 0,  $mask_M$  to NaN
5:   initialize  $a_i$  with  $mask_i$ 
6:    $sum \leftarrow 0$ 
7:   for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
8:      $pos \leftarrow \lceil exp(x_i) / SHIFT \rceil + 2$     $\triangleright exp()$  extracts biased exponent
9:      $(a_{pos}, e) \leftarrow FastTwoSum(a_{pos}, x_i)$ 
10:     $a_{pos-2} \leftarrow fl(a_{pos-2} + e)$ 
11:    if  $(i \bmod C1) == 0$  then            $\triangleright C1 =$  capacity of normal buckets
12:      for  $j = 1$  to  $M - 2$  do            $\triangleright$  Tidy up normal buckets
13:         $r \leftarrow fl(fl(mask_{j+1} + fl(a_j - mask_j)) - mask_{j+1})$ 
14:         $a_{j+1} \leftarrow fl(a_{j+1} + r)$ 
15:         $a_j \leftarrow fl(a_j - r)$ 
16:      end for
17:    end if
18:    if  $(i \bmod C2) == 0$  then            $\triangleright C2 =$  capacity of overflow buckets
19:       $sum \leftarrow fl(sum + fl(a_{M-1} - mask_{M-1}))$     $\triangleright$  Tidy up overflow
20:       $a_{M-1} \leftarrow mask_{M-1}$ 
21:    end if
22:  end for
23:  for  $i = 1$  to  $M - 1$  do            $\triangleright$  remove masks
24:     $a_i \leftarrow a_i - mask_i$ 
25:  end for
26:  return ModifiedKahanSum( $sum, a_{M-1}$  downto 1,  $M - 1$ )
27: end function

```

Axiom 1. *The "unit in the first place" (Chapter 2.2) of a bucket is immutable except for the underflow or overflow range.*

Axiom 1 means that during the summation process the significance of the most significant bit of each bucket may not change. Otherwise it is not possible to rely on a fixed exponent range for each bucket. To archive that, the leading bit pattern "11" has been introduced. Under the assumption, that the most significant bit of bucket i is 2^i , each number less than 2^{i-1} may be added or subtracted without changing the

■ **Figure 4.2.:** Four possible examples for partitioning and storing the error of the smallest allowed addend into the neighbouring bucket.

significance of the first bit of the bucket. This property is well known from integer arithmetic.

Assumption 1. *The exponent range of floating-point numbers is unlimited.*

Assumption 1 allows to ignore the under- and overflow-range for now. These two ranges will be treated in Chapter 4.2.2 for the special case of binary64 values.

Theorem 1. *The summation error of bucket i has to be added at least to bucket $i - 2$.*

Proof. The proof for Theorem 1 will be done graphically in Figure 4.2. In that Figure it is obvious, that independent of the bit lengths $part_1$, $part_2$ and $part_3$ the full bit precision p of the addend cannot be preserved. Therefore the summation error of bucket i has to be added at least to bucket $i - 2$, like shown in Figure 4.3. In Algorithm 7, line 10, this action is performed. \square

Assumption 2. *The summation error of bucket i is added to bucket $i - 2$.*

The choice of the error bucket is dependent on the size $shift$. The "further away" the error bucket is, the smaller $shift$ has to be, as one might deduce from Figure

4. ACCURATE SUMMATION

■ **Figure 4.3.:** Error storage scenario of the smallest allowed addend into bucket $i - 2$.

4.3. And the smaller $shift$ is, the more buckets are required. Assumption 2 takes the first possible error bucket according to Theorem 1, in order to reduce the number of required buckets.

Theorem 2. For Axiom 1 and the Assumptions 1 and 2, the following rules have to apply to the lengths $part_1$, $part_2$, and $part_3 + guard$, in order to get a ternary bucket partition, that maximizes the lengths $part_1$ and $part_2$:

1. $guard + part_3 = \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil$
2. $\left\lceil \frac{\left\lfloor \frac{2}{3}(p-1) \right\rfloor}{2} \right\rceil \leq part_2 \leq \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil$
3. $part_1 = p - 2 - part_2 - \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil$

Proof. From Figure 4.3 three useful equations can be derived:

$$p = 2 + part_1 + guard + part_2 + part_3 \quad (4.2)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} max. error = p - (part_3 + 1) \\ max. error \leq 2 \cdot part_2 \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow part_3 \geq p - 2 \cdot part_2 - 1 \quad (4.3)$$

$$2 \cdot part_2 \leq guard + part_2 + part_3 \Leftrightarrow part_2 \leq guard + part_3 \quad (4.4)$$

By reformulating equation 4.2 to $(part_1 + part_2) + (guard + part_3) = const.$, one can derive two equivalent objective functions $max. part_1 + part_2 \Leftrightarrow$

$\min. guard + part_3$. For the latter one, a constrained optimization problem is given in 4.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{minimize} && guard + part_3 \\
 &\text{subject to} && part_3 \geq p - 2 \cdot part_2 - 1 \\
 &&& part_2 \leq guard + part_3 \\
 &&& guard \geq 0 \\
 &&& part_3 \geq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

The optimization problem 4.5 can be relaxed to the problem 4.6 with additionally combining the first two constraints.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{minimize} && guard + part_3 \\
 &\text{subject to} && 3 \cdot part_3 + 2 \cdot guard \geq p - 1 \\
 &&& guard \geq 0 \\
 &&& part_3 \geq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.6}$$

As $part_3$ has the larger factor in the first constraint of 4.6, an optimum can be obtained for $guard = 0$ in equation 4.7.

$$guard + part_3 = \frac{p-1}{3} \tag{4.7}$$

By respecting $guard$ and $part_3$ to be integers, an upward rounding of this optimum, to fulfil the optimization constraints, yields the first equation of Theorem 2. With the first equation of Theorem 2 and equation 4.4 an upper bound for $part_2$ is found:

$$part_2 \leq guard + part_3 = \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil \tag{4.8}$$

A lower bound is obtained by combining $part_3 \leq guard + part_3$ and equation 4.3:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil \geq p - 2 \cdot part_2 - 1 \\
 \Leftrightarrow & part_2 \geq \frac{p-1 - \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil}{2} = \frac{\left\lfloor \frac{2}{3}(p-1) \right\rfloor}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

Respecting the integer property of $part_2$ and by combining the equations 4.8 and 4.9, the second equation of Theorem 2 is derived. Inserting the first equation of Theorem 2 into equation 4.2 yields the third equation of Theorem 2. \square

Assumption 3. *In the first equation of Theorem 2, guard is maximized.*

With Theorem 2 only an equation for the sum of $guard$ and $part_3$ was derived. As earlier described, $guard$ is an extension $part_2$, at the cost of $part_3$, which is of minor importance. Therefore it is more desirable to maximize $guard$ (Assumption 3). This allows to define $guard$ more precisely in Theorem 3.

Theorem 3. *Under the Assumption 3 and with Theorem 2*

$$guard = 3 \cdot \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil - (p-1).$$

Proof. According to Theorem 2 $guard + part_3$ is constant. This means maximizing $guard$ is equivalent to minimizing $part_3$. A lower bound for $part_3$ is given in equation 4.3. Combined with the upper bound of shift from the second equation of Theorem 2, yields:

$$part_3 \geq p - 1 - 2 \cdot \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil \quad (4.10)$$

Due to the minimization of $part_3$, 4.10 becomes an equation. This inserted into the first equation of Theorem 2, proofs Theorem 3. \square

All possible relations between $shift$ and p can be seen in Figure 4.4. In the following, the number of addends, that can be accumulated without losing any significant bits, are described by Theorem 4.

Theorem 4. *Given the bucket partition of Theorem 2, up to $N < 2^{part_1}$ additions to a bucket can be performed without violating Axiom 1.*

Proof. Without loss of generality, the by magnitude largest allowed number to be added to a bucket with a "unit in the first place" 2^i is $2^{(i-part_1-1)} - 2^{(i-p+1)} < 2^{(i-part_1-1)}$. The bucket is initialized with $2^i + 2^{(i-1)}$, thus it will not overflow for $2^{(i-1)} > N \cdot 2^{(i-part_1-1)} \Leftrightarrow 2^{part_1} > N$. \square

Finally a complexity analysis of *BucketSum* (Algorithm 7) similar to that one in [ZH10, Chapter 2.1] should be done. For each of the N addends the following operations have to be performed:

1	1	$shift - 3$	2	$shift$	$shift - 2$	$p = 3 \cdot shift - 1$
1	1	$shift - 2$	1	$shift$	$shift - 1$	$p = 3 \cdot shift$
1	1	$shift - 1$		$shift$	$shift$	$p = 3 \cdot shift + 1$
1	1	$shift - 1$		$shift$	$shift + 1$	$p = 3 \cdot shift + 2$

■ **Figure 4.4.:** All possible ternary partitions for a given $shift$. Note that $p = 3 \cdot shift - 2$ violates the upper bound of $shift$ in Theorem 2.

- Bucket determination (line 8): 3 FLOPs²
- *FastTwoSum* (line 9): 3 FLOPs
- Error summation (line 10): 1 FLOP

After C2 steps, the overflow bucket has to be tidied up, that requires two additional FLOPs (lines 18-21). After C1 steps, all $M - 2$ buckets need to be tidied up. This requires five additional FLOPs (lines 11-17) per bucket as well. Once in the end an unmasking has to happen with $M - 1$ FLOPs (lines 23-25) and for the final sum up, Algorithm 6 (line 26) requires $((M - 1) \cdot 4) + 1$ more FLOPs. All in all

$$N \cdot 7 + \left\lfloor \frac{N}{C2} \right\rfloor \cdot 2 + \left\lfloor \frac{N}{C1} \right\rfloor \cdot (M - 2) \cdot 5 + \underbrace{(M - 1) + ((M - 1) \cdot 4) + 1}_{\text{Final sum up}} \quad [FLOPs]$$

are required. Assume a large number of addends $N \gg M$. Then the final sum up part has a small static contribution to the complexity, thus it can be neglected. If the buckets don't have to be tidied up during the summation for small $N \leq C2 \leq C1$, an overall complexity of $7N$ remains. Even if $N \geq C1 \geq C2$ holds, the effort for tidying up is small compared to the seven FLOPs, that always have to be performed. Thus the complexity of *BucketSum* is considered to be $7N$.

²For simplicity integer operations are counted as FLOPs.

4.2.2. Realization for binary64

The binary64 type has the precision $p = 53$. Therefore we get $shift = \left\lceil \frac{p-1}{3} \right\rceil = 18$ and a significant partitioning by Theorems 2 and 3, as shown in Figure 4.5.

■ **Figure 4.5.:** Significant partition for binary64.

Also one can no longer assume an infinite exponent range. Assumption 1 has to be replaced by a concrete bucket alignment. This alignment consists of three parts, the under- and overflow and the normal bucket part. The anchor for the alignment is, that the least significant bit of the *shift* part of the first normal bucket $a[0]$ has the significance of the biased exponent 0. This anchor has been chosen, because no binary64, even the subnormal numbers with a biased exponent of 0, can be accumulated into a bucket smaller than $a[0]$. All in all to cover the full exponent range of binary64, one needs $\lceil 2^{11}/shift \rceil = 114$ buckets. Beginning with the first normal bucket $a[0]$, each following bucket is aligned with a unit in the first place of *shift* bigger than its predecessor. The maximal multiple of *shift* that fits in this pattern is $\lfloor 2^{11}/shift \rfloor = 113$. Therefore we define the topmost bucket to be an overflow bucket. This bucket is responsible for values with a unit in the first place of greater than 2^{1011} , but these values are ignored in this work. With an unreasonable effort, this overflow situation can be handled differently. The second overflow bucket needs an exceptional alignment as well. Its $part_1$ is smaller due to upper limit of the binary64 exponent range 2^{1023} . Because of the alignment of $a[0]$ and Assumption 2, two additional error buckets for the underflow range are required. For the underflow range $[2^{-1023}, 2^{-1074}]$, bucket $a[-1]$ follows the alignment scheme of the normal buckets and bucket $a[-2]$ is responsible for the remaining bit positions. The exponent range partition is illustrated in Figure 4.6. Graphical visualizations of the bucket alignment in the under- and overflow range are given in the Figures D.1 and D.2.

■ **Figure 4.6.:** Exponent range partition.

Finally the accumulation reserve for the normal and underflow buckets is according to Theorem 4 smaller than 2^{15} . For the first overflow bucket one obtains analogue to Theorem 4 an accumulation reserve of less than 2^{11} .

4.2.3. Implementation

One essential element of this Master's Thesis is the efficient implementation of *BucketSum*. This chapter deals with all implementation details and changes to the pseudo-code from Algorithm 7. Some potential improvements to a floating-point using software are described in Chapters 3.3 and 3.4. The in Chapter 3.4 presented technique of partial loop unrolling can be used to obtain an elegant side effect for the tidy up and sum up steps. In Algorithm 7 all buckets are initialized with an appropriate mask. This mask has to be considered in the tidy up process (lines 13 and 19-20) and it has to be removed before the final sum up (lines 23-25). If two different bucket arrays $a1$ and $a2$ are used, $a1$ uses the masks as described in Algorithm 7 and $a2$ uses the negative masks. In that way the exact sum of the unmasked values of the buckets i can be computed by $a1[i] + a2[i]$. This way the number of floating-point operations dealing with masking and unmasking are reduced a lot. Additionally the partial loop unrolling increases the instruction-level parallelism and finally increases the tidy up values by a factor of two. This means that less tidy up "interruptions" for the N addends are required.

Another considered optimization is the avoidance of the division by the *shift* in Algorithm 7 line 8. An integer division is an expensive operation compared to

multiplication and bit shifting. In [Fog13, Pages 51-52] one can find latencies for several instructions. For the AMD "Piledriver" the latency for a signed or unsigned division ((I)DIV [AMD13b, Pages 159-160 and 163-164]) ranges from 12-71 clock cycles. Compared to this the sum of the latencies of a left or right bit shift (SHL/SHR [AMD13b, Pages 292 and 295-296]) with one clock cycle and a signed or unsigned multiplication ((I)MUL [AMD13b, Pages 165-166 and 235-236]) with 4-6 clock cycles is by far smaller. As this division by the *shift* has to be done for each addends exponent, a small speed up could be archived by replacing the division by a multiplication followed by a bit shift, as shown in Listing 4.1. The idea behind the values of Listing 4.1 is an integer optimization problem.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && x + y \\ & \text{subject to} && \frac{exp}{18} = \frac{x \cdot exp}{2^y}, \forall exp \in [0, 2047) \\ & && x > 0 \\ & && y > 0. \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

For normal and subnormal binary64 the exponents range from 0 to 2046 and the desired division should be a cheap bit shift, thus a power of two. Therefore the task is to find for the smallest possible power of two y some minimal $x = \left\lceil \frac{2^y}{18} \right\rceil$. This x was found with the program of Listing 4.2.

```
1 double d = 1.0;
2 // Exponent extraction
3 unsigned position = ((ieee754_double *) (&d))->exponent;
4
5 // Perform equivalent operations
6 unsigned pos1 = position / 18;
7 unsigned pos2 = (position * 1821) >> 15;
```

■ **Listing 4.1:** Division by 18 replacement.

```
1 #include <cmath>
2 #include <iostream>
3
4 int
5 main ()
6 {
7     unsigned div = 1;
8
9     // Try some powers of two (div = 2^y)
10    for (unsigned y = 1; y < 32; y++)
11        {
12            div *= 2;
13            unsigned x = (unsigned) std::ceil ((double) div / 18.0);
14
15            // Test all exponents of the IEEE 754 - 2008 binary64 normal and
16            // subnormal range
17            int is_valid = 1;
18            for (unsigned i = 0; i < 2047; i++)
19                is_valid &= ((i / 18) == ((i * x) / div));
20            if (is_valid)
21                std::cout << "Found: " << x << " / 2^" << y << std::endl;
22        }
23
24    return 0;
25 }
```

■ **Listing 4.2:** Program to solve the integer optimization problem (Equation 4.11).

4.3. Benchmark

The benchmark program compares the five summation algorithms of Table 4.1 with their source of implementation mentioned in brackets. The accurate summation results of the C-XSC toolbox will be used as reference values for the five types of test data.

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Algorithm	FLOPs	Run-time	Space
Ordinary Recursive Summation (Algorithm 2)	$N - 1$	1	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
SumK (K = 2, [Lat12])	$(3K - 2)N$	2-3	$\mathcal{O}(N)$
iFastSum ([ZH10])	$> 6N$	3-5 [†]	$\mathcal{O}(N)$
OnlineExactSum ([ZH10])	$5N$	4-6* [‡]	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
BucketSum (Algorithm 7)	$7N$	1-2*	$\mathcal{O}(1)$

■ **Table 4.1.:** Comparison of summation algorithms for input data length N .

* With instruction-level parallelism.

† Results for Data 3 omitted.

‡ Only for large dimension.

The test data for the summation benchmark program is chosen similar to [ZH10, Chapter 3]. **Data 1** are N random, positive floating-point numbers, all with an exponent of 2^0 . Thus Data 1 is pretty well-conditioned $R_{\text{summation}} = 1$. **Data 2** is ill-conditioned. The exponents are distributed uniformly and randomly between 2^{-900} and 2^{900} , the signs are assigned randomly and the significant is filled randomly as well. **Data 3** is similar to Data 2, but its sum is exactly zero. **Data 4** is Anderson’s ill-conditioned data [And99, Chapter 4]. And finally **Data 5** is designed to especially stress the accumulation reserve of *BucketSum*. A visualization of that test case is given in Figure D.3.

For time measurement the *clock()* function [ISO11a, Chapter 7.27.2.1] [ISO11b, Chapter 20.11.8] is used. To keep the time measurement as accurate as possible, all memory operations like array creation and destruction should be kept outside of time measuring code blocks. On the other hand, if the size of the input data N was chosen too small, the measured time is too inaccurate. This requires a certain number of repeated operations R , to obtain detectable results. But some algorithms like *SumK* and *iFastSum* operate inline on the input data. Thus providing a single copy of the data will not suffice to get identical initial conditions for each repetition. To meet all these constraints, a large copy of $R \cdot (N + 1)$ elements for summation is created, each of the repeated N elements with a leading zero, as *iFastSum* and *BucketSum* imitate Fortran indexing. The systems available main memory creates another constraint on the maximum test case size $R \cdot (N + 1)$. This product should not exceed the test systems 8 GB of main memory, otherwise the timings will become inaccurate due to

swapping to hard disk. This means for $R = 1$ repetitions the theoretical maximum test case size can be $N = \frac{8 \cdot 1024^3 \text{Byte}}{8 \text{Byte}} - 1 = 1.073.741.823 \geq 10^9$ elements. Experimental test runs revealed, that about 10^7 elements are necessary in order to obtain detectable results. Therefore the following data lengths and repetitions are defined:

- Middle dimension: $[10^3, 10^4]$ elements with 10^4 repetitions
- Large dimension: $[10^6, 10^7]$ elements with 10^1 repetitions

The benchmarks (Figures 4.7 and 4.8) show, that *BucketSum* performs best for all given kinds of data. *BucketSum* is by factor 2-3 slower than the Ordinary Recursive Summation and is slightly faster than *SumK* (with $K = 2$). For middle and large data lengths *BucketSum* scales linear in contrast to *OnlineExactSum*, which starts to scale linear at a data length of about $6 \cdot 10^3$ elements. Another interesting observation is, that *OnlineExactSum* is dependent on the condition of the input data $R_{\text{summation}}$ for small data lengths. For *iFastSum*, *OnlineExactSum* and *BucketSum* the results have been compared to that one of the C-XSC toolbox using an *assert()* [ISO11b, Chapter 19.3] statement, thus any inaccurate result would have interrupted the benchmark. As no interruptions occurred, all three algorithms are assumed to deliver correctly rounded sums. The most important properties of the algorithms under test are summarized in Table 4.1, which is a modified extension of [ZH10, Table V].

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■ **Figure 4.7.:** Benchmark results summation of middle dimension input data.

Figure 4.8.: Benchmark results summation of large dimension input data.

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Accurate inner product

This chapter is the combination of all previous chapters. With the FMA instruction and an efficient and fast summation algorithm, one is able to create efficient inner product algorithms as well. After a short overview about previous approaches, three algorithms using FMA will be introduced.

5.1. Previous work

Like the Recursive summation (Algorithm 2), there also exists a simple straight forward implementation of the inner product, namely Algorithm 8 (see [MBdD⁺10, Algorithm 6.2]). A condition number for the inner product (Equation 5.1) is defined in [MBdD⁺10, Chapter 6.1.2] as well:

$$R_{\text{dot product}} = \frac{2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n |a_i \cdot b_i|}{\left| \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot b_i \right|} \quad (5.1)$$

Similar to the definition of the error-free transformation for the sum, there also exists a definition for the product in [ORO05, Chapter 3]:

$$a \cdot b = x + y \quad \text{and} \quad x = fl(a \cdot b) \quad (5.2)$$

Algorithm 8 Recursive inner product.

```

1: function RECURSIVEDOTPRODUCT( $a, b, N$ )
2:    $s \leftarrow fl(a_1 \cdot b_1)$ 
3:   for  $i = 2$  to  $N$  do
4:      $s \leftarrow fl(s + fl(a_i \cdot b_i))$ 
5:   end for
6:   return  $s$ 
7: end function

```

This means the product is transformed into a sum. By knowing this, it becomes obvious why the task of finding an efficient inner product algorithm is strongly connected with the task of accurate summation. If the factors are floating-point numbers $a, b \in \mathbb{F}$, then $x, y \in \mathbb{F}$ holds, like for the error-free transformation of the sum, too. $x \in \mathbb{F}$ follows from the definition in Equation 5.2. An example for $y \in \mathbb{F}$ for the special case of binary64 is given in Equation 5.3. If a and b have the biggest possible significant (all bits set to "1"), then their product cannot exceed 106 bits. This fits exactly into two 53 bit precisions of a binary64.

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= (2^{53} - 2^0) \cdot 2^{exp_a} \\
 b &= (2^{53} - 2^0) \cdot 2^{exp_b} \\
 c &= a \cdot b = (2^{106} - 2^{54} + 2^0) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \\
 x &= fl(c) = (2^{106} - 2^{54}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \\
 y &= a \cdot b - fl(c) = (2^0) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

Without the FMA instruction, there exists the algorithm *TwoProduct*, that is able to perform this error-free product transformation by using 17 FLOPs (see [ORO05, Chapter 3] for details). Having a system with a hardware implemented FMA instruction, the whole effort can be reduced to *TwoProductFMA* (Algorithm 9). This algorithm is also described in [ORO05, Algorithm 3.5] and requires only two FLOPs.

For the inner product the idea of error-free transformation can also be extended from two to N operands with *Dot2* (Algorithm 10). *Dot2* computes $\sum_{i=1}^N x_i \cdot y_i$ as

Algorithm 9 Error-free transformation TwoProductFMA.

```
1: function TWOPRODUCTFMA( $a, b$ )
2:    $x \leftarrow fl(a \cdot b)$ 
3:    $y \leftarrow FMA(a, b, -x)$ 
4:   return ( $x, y$ )
5: end function
```

if twice the working precision was used [ORO05, Chapter 5]. In that paper the idea has been extended to algorithm *DotK*, which can evaluate the inner product, as if computed with K -fold working precision. A slightly modified version of *Dot2* will be presented in the next chapter.

Algorithm 10 Inner product in twice the working precision Dot2.

```
1: function DOT2( $x, y, N$ )
2:    $[p, s] \leftarrow TwoProduct(x_1, y_1)$ 
3:   for  $i = 2$  to  $N$  do
4:      $[h, r] \leftarrow TwoProduct(x_i, y_i)$ 
5:      $[p, q] \leftarrow TwoSum(p, h)$ 
6:      $s \leftarrow fl(s + fl(q + r))$ 
7:   end for
8:   return  $fl(p + s)$ 
9: end function
```

5.2. Algorithms based upon TwoProductFMA

The first algorithm that is tested in the following benchmark (Chapter 5.3) is *Dot2* (Algorithm 10) with all occurrences of *TwoProduct* replaced by *TwoProductFMA*. This algorithm will be called *Dot2FMA* in the following. This modification is already described in [ORO05, Chapter 5].

Another trivial idea is not to modify the existing summation algorithms of Chapter 4. Instead a preprocessing of the input vectors is done with *TwoProductFMA* (Algorithm 9). This approach will be called *FMAWrapperDotProd* and is described in Algorithm 11 in combination with *BucketSum*. *FMAWrapperDotProd* has two major flaws. The first one is connected with the data preprocessing. The implementer has to

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decide whether the method should preserve the input vectors or not. In the first case the memory requirement increases by twice the size of the input vector length, in the latter case the original input vectors are lost. The second flaw is related to the usage of the summation algorithm in Algorithm 11 lines 7-8. These lines create an intermediate rounding, that dependent on the resulting vectors can return a not correctly rounded result. A solution to this problem would be an interface method, that allows to accumulate a vector of a certain size, and a second one to make a final sum up to a correctly rounded sum. Such an interface is for example available in the implementation of *OnlineExactSum* [ZH10].

Algorithm 11 FMAWrapperDotProd.

Input: N , number of addends

Input: x , first array of length N

Input: y , second array of length N

Output: s , computed inner product $\sum_{i=1}^N x_i \cdot y_i$

```

1: function FMAWRAPPERDOTPROD( $x, y, N$ )
2:   for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do                                     ▷ In-place array preprocessing
3:      $t \leftarrow fl(x_i \cdot y_i)$                              ▷ Destructive TwoProductFMA
4:      $y_i \leftarrow FMA(x_i, y_i, -t)$ 
5:      $x_i \leftarrow t$ 
6:   end for
7:    $s \leftarrow BucketSum(x, N)$                                ▷ Any summation algorithm possible
8:    $s \leftarrow fl(s + BucketSum(y, N))$ 
9:   return  $s$ 
10: end function

```

Finally a modified version of *BucketSum* (Algorithm 7) is presented, namely *BucketDotProd* (Algorithm 12). *BucketDotProd* is identical to *BucketSum*, except for the lines 8-13, where *TwoProductFMA* comes into play. Assume the product to accumulate is $a \cdot b$, therefore $x = fl(a \cdot b)$ and $y = FMA(a, b, -a \cdot b)$. It was already shown, that if x has to be added to bucket i and its error to bucket $i - 2$, no significant bit is lost (Theorem 1). In order to avoid the expensive three FLOPs for the exponent extraction of y , one can make use of the *shift* = 18 property for the binary64 realization. In that case y will always fall in the exponent range of bucket $i - 3$. According to Theorem 1 the error of y has to be added to bucket $i - 5$.

Algorithm 12 BucketDotProd.

Input: N , number of addends

Input: x , first array of length N
Input: y , second array of length N
Output: s , correctly rounded inner product $\sum_{i=1}^N x_i * y_i$

```

1: function BUCKETDOTPROD( $x, y, N$ )
2:      $\triangleright a_1$  and  $a_2$  are underflow and  $a_{M-1}$  and  $a_M$  are overflow buckets
3:     create arrays of  $M$  buckets  $a$   $\triangleright a_{2\dots M-2}$  cover SHIFT exponents
4:     create arrays of  $M$  bucket masks  $mask$   $\triangleright mask_1$  is set to 0,  $mask_M$  to NaN
5:     initialize  $a_i$  with  $mask_i$ 
6:      $sum \leftarrow 0$ 
7:     for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
8:          $(v, w) \leftarrow TwoProductFMA(x_i, y_i)$ 
9:          $pos \leftarrow \lceil exp(v)/SHIFT \rceil + 2$   $\triangleright exp()$  extracts biased exponent
10:         $(a_{pos}, e_1) \leftarrow FastTwoSum(a_{pos}, v)$ 
11:         $(a_{pos-3}, e_2) \leftarrow FastTwoSum(a_{pos-3}, w)$ 
12:         $a_{pos-2} \leftarrow fl(a_{pos-2} + e_1)$ 
13:         $a_{pos-5} \leftarrow fl(a_{pos-5} + e_2)$ 
14:        if  $(i \bmod C1) == 0$  then  $\triangleright C1 =$  capacity of normal buckets
15:            for  $j = 1$  to  $M - 2$  do  $\triangleright$  Tidy up normal buckets
16:                 $r \leftarrow fl(fl(mask_{j+1} + fl(a_j - mask_j)) - mask_{j+1})$ 
17:                 $a_{j+1} \leftarrow fl(a_{j+1} + r)$ 
18:                 $a_j \leftarrow fl(a_j - r)$ 
19:            end for
20:        end if
21:        if  $(i \bmod C2) == 0$  then  $\triangleright C2 =$  capacity of overflow buckets
22:             $sum \leftarrow fl(sum + fl(a_{M-1} - mask_{M-1}))$   $\triangleright$  Tidy up overflow
23:             $a_{M-1} \leftarrow mask_{M-1}$ 
24:        end if
25:    end for
26:    for  $i = 1$  to  $M - 1$  do  $\triangleright$  remove masks
27:         $a_i \leftarrow a_i - mask_i$ 
28:    end for
29:    return ModifiedKahanSum( $sum, a_{M-1}$  downto 1,  $M - 1$ )
30: end function

```

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■ **Figure 5.1.:** Visualization of BucketDotProds accumulation.

This chapter shows, that with moderate effort nearly each summation algorithm can be modified to handle the task of inner product computation as well. In the following numerical tests show the properties of these three algorithms in a benchmark program.

5.3. Benchmark

For the benchmark of inner product the five algorithms of Table 5.1 are compared. All algorithms were implemented as part of this Master’s Thesis. Only for the implementation of *Dot2* and *Dot2FMA* some sub-functions of [Lat12] were used. Like for the summation benchmark the C-XSC toolbox has been used to verify the correctness of the computed inner products.

Algorithm	FLOPs	Run-time	Space
Recursive Inner Product (Algorithm 8)	$2N - 1$	1	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
Dot2 (Algorithm 10)	$25N - 7$	5-6	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
Dot2FMA (Algorithm 10)	$6N - 3$	3-4	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
FMAWrapperDotProd (Algorithm 11)	$16N$	4-6*	$\mathcal{O}(N)$
BucketDotProd (Algorithm 12)	$13N$	3-4*	$\mathcal{O}(1)$

■ **Table 5.1.:** Comparison of inner product algorithms for input data length N .

* With instruction-level parallelism.

For the inner product benchmark four kinds of test data are used. **Data 1** are two random, positive floating-point vectors of length N , all with an exponent of 2^0 . **Data 2** is well-conditioned like Data 1, but each of the two input vectors has a random distributed exponent range between 2^0 and 2^{400} . **Data 3** is ill-conditioned with a random

distributed exponent between 2^{-400} and 2^{400} . Finally **Data 4** is ill-conditioned, with a real inner product of exactly zero. The time measuring and the determination of the middle and large dimension data lengths happens in the same way as in Chapter 4.3. Especially the assumptions for the data length determination allows the creation of two arrays, without exceeding the available main memory.

■ **Figure 5.2.:** Benchmark results inner product of middle dimension input data.

The results of the inner product benchmark, shown in Figures 5.2 and 5.3, verify a linear scaling of the algorithms in Table 5.1 for data lengths in each, middle and large dimension. Another observation is, that the type of the data does not really affect the runtime of the algorithms. In any case *BucketDotProd* is the fastest algorithm and only by factor 2-3 slower than the Recursive Inner Product. *FMAWrapperDotProd*,

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Figure 5.3.: Benchmark results inner product of large dimension input data.

that only preprocesses the input vectors, is already by factor 4-6 slower than the Recursive Inner Product. The reason for this seems to be, that all input vectors have to be processed completely twice. Another improvement is observable if *Dot2* is used in combination with *TwoProductFMA* in *Dot2FMA*. The execution time nearly halves, if a hardware implemented FMA instruction is available on the system. The result accuracy is again checked by an *assert()*-statement against the result of the C-XSC toolbox, like it was done for the summation benchmark. Therefore the results of *BucketDotProd* are claimed to be correctly rounded. This check cannot be applied for *FMAWrapperDotProd*, because of the in the previous chapter discussed implementation drawback.

Conclusion

In this chapter the results of the previous chapters should be summarized. After giving the reader an overview about binary floating-point arithmetic in Chapter 2, an efficient way of extracting the exponent part of a binary64 was described by using bit operations. The standard library functions did not provide the desired performance. A very desirable future development would be, that a successive version of IEEE 754-2008 addresses this feature. Then hardware vendors need to provide a high speed function on hardware level. The existing *fxtract*, is slower than simple bit level operations, as it has to extract the significant part additionally and that there do not exist vectorized versions of it. In Chapter 3 it was shown, that the upcoming hardware supported FMA instruction performs as like as other arithmetic operations and that all features of IEEE 754-2008, especially the rounding property, are given. For the FMA instruction the desired development, first a specification, then a very efficient hardware realization, already happened.

The Chapters 4 and 5 were dedicated to the development of the efficient and accurate summation algorithm *BucketSum* and its extension to an inner product algorithm *BucketDotProd*. After giving the reader an overview of the respective operation, it was shown, that computing the inner product is closely related to summation via the property of error-free product transformation. All algorithm implementations of these chapters try to make as much use of the given system features as possible. For example techniques like partial loop unrolling make more use of the processor pipeline, com-

piling with the flag `-march=native` enables the usage of AVX and FMA instructions, if available. But the presented algorithms are not perfect in any case. Depending on the system and the used data format and the data lengths themselves, parameters of the partitioning might have been chosen differently to for example increase the accumulation reserve. Therefore the description of *BucketSum* was intended to be as generic as possible to enable a fast adaptation to different environments. Chapter 5 also shows, that a new hardware implemented function can result in a huge gain of performance for many existing algorithms, that were considered to be too expensive, if the operation has to be emulated by other basic floating-point operations. As a representative example, *TwoProduct* could be reduced from 17 FLOPs to two. This makes error-free product transformation more interesting for other applications. The realization of a more ambitious demand by Kulish [Kul13, Chapter 8], to even fully implement the accurate sum and inner product by hardware, would be interesting for the future as well. But as long as these operations are not standardized, no hardware vendor might be interested in such a realization.

The application field of the presented algorithms is quite large, as summation and inner products are very elementary operations. Possible future works might use these algorithms for verified computations or to tune their parameters to be extended to whole matrix operations, like for example the residual computation for iterative methods. The residual computation

$$r_i = (A^i, -1) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{x} \\ b_i \end{pmatrix}$$

is basically nothing more than a matrix-vector product and thus several inner product computations. All in all dealing with elementary operations offers many possibilities to tie in with further works.

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Test system information

The test system used throughout this Master's Thesis is described in this chapter.

A.1. Software

Property	Value
Operating system	Ubuntu 13.10
Linux kernel version	3.11
Compiler	gcc 4.8.1
C library	eglibc 2.17

■ **Table A.1.:** Software properties of the test system.

```
1 # kernel information
2 uname -a
3
4 # compiler and C library information
5 gcc --version
6 ldd --version
```

■ **Listing A.1:** Linux commands to verify the system software properties.

A.2. Hardware

Property	Value
Notebook name	HP g6-2239eg
Microprocessor	2.3 GHz AMD Quad-Core A10-4600M APU with Radeon HD 7660G/7670M Dual Graphics
Microarchitecture	Piledriver [You12]
Chipset	AMD A70M FCH
Microprocessor Cache	4 MB L2 cache
Memory	8 GB DDR3

■ **Table A.2.:** Hardware properties of the test system. Taken from <http://h10025.www1.hp.com/ewfrf/wc/document?docname=c03550353&lc=en>.

```
1 # CPU information
2 cat /proc/cpuinfo
3 dmidecode -t processor
4
5 # memory information
6 free -b
7 dmidecode -t memory
```

■ **Listing A.2:** Linux commands to verify the system hardware properties.

FMA test cases

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= (1 + 2^{-30}) \cdot 2^{exp_a} \\
 b &= (1 + 2^{-23}) \cdot 2^{exp_b} \\
 c &= (1 + 2^{-23} + 2^{-30}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \\
 a \cdot b &= \left(1 + 2^{-23} + 2^{-30} + \underbrace{2^{-53}}_{\text{round bit}} \right) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \\
 fl(a \cdot b) &= (1 + 2^{-23} + 2^{-30} + 2^{-52}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \quad \text{roundTowardPositive} \\
 fl(a \cdot b) &= (1 + 2^{-23} + 2^{-30}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b} \quad \text{roundTowardNegative} \\
 &\quad \text{or roundTiesToEven} \\
 fl(a \cdot b - c) &= \underline{\underline{(2^{-53}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b}}} \quad \text{result with FMA and any rounding mode} \\
 fl(fl(a \cdot b) - c) &= \underline{\underline{(2^{-52}) \cdot 2^{exp_a + exp_b}}} \quad \text{roundTowardPositive} \\
 fl(fl(a \cdot b) - c) &= \underline{\underline{0}} \quad \text{roundTowardNegative or roundTiesToEven}
 \end{aligned}$$

■ **Figure B.1.:** Mathematical description of FMA test case 1.

B. FMA TEST CASES

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= \left(1 + 2^{-30}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a} \\
 b &= \left(1 + 2^{-52}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_b} \\
 c &= \left(1 + 2^{-30}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b} \\
 a \cdot b &= \left(1 + 2^{-30} + 2^{-52} + \underbrace{2^{-82}}_{\text{sticky bit}}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b} \\
 fl(a \cdot b) &= \left(1 + 2^{-30} + 2^{-51}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b} \quad \text{roundTowardPositive} \\
 fl(a \cdot b) &= \left(1 + 2^{-30} + 2^{-52}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b} \quad \text{roundTowardNegative} \\
 &\quad \text{or roundTiesToEven} \\
 fl(a \cdot b - c) &= \underline{\underline{\left(2^{-52} + 2^{-82}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b}}} \quad \text{result with FMA and any rounding mode} \\
 fl(fl(a \cdot b) - c) &= \underline{\underline{\left(2^{-51}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b}}} \quad \text{roundTowardPositive} \\
 fl(fl(a \cdot b) - c) &= \underline{\underline{\left(2^{-52}\right) \cdot 2^{exp_a+exp_b}}} \quad \text{roundTowardNegative or roundTiesToEven}
 \end{aligned}$$

■ **Figure B.2.:** Mathematical description of FMA test case 2.

```

1  /* ... */
2
3     double x = 1.0 + std::pow (2.0, -30.0);
4     double y = 1.0 + std::pow (2.0, -23.0);
5     double z = -(1.0 + std::pow (2.0, -23.0) + std::pow (2.0, -30.0));
6 #if !defined(NO_FMA)
7     double expect = std::pow (2.0, -53.0);
8 #elif (ROUNDING_MODE == FE_UPWARD)
9     double expect = std::pow (2.0, -52.0);
10 #else
11     double expect = 0.0;
12 #endif
13
14 /* ... */
15
16 // Try to set rounding mode
17 int error = std::fesetround (ROUNDING_MODE);
18
19 /* ... */
20
21 // Initialize data
22 for (int i = 0; i < DATA_LENGTH; i++)
23 {
24     v1[i] = x;
25     v2[i] = y;
26     v3[i] = z;
27 }
28 for (int i = 0; i < PARALLEL; i++)
29     a[i] = 0.0;
30
31 /* ... */
32
33 a[0] += std::fma (v1[j], v2[j], v3[j]);
34
35 /* ... */
36
37 a[0] += (v1[j] * v2[j]) + v3[j];
38
39 /* ... */

```

■ **Listing B.1:** Excerpts of the FMA test case 1 implementation.

```

1  .L15:
2     # ...
3     vfmaddsd    (%r12), %xmm5, %xmm4, %xmm2 # *v3_20, tmp107, tmp106, D.37327
4     vfmadd231sd 8(%rbx), %xmm6, %xmm1      # MEM[(double *)v2_18 + 8B], tmp108, ✓
        D.37327

```

■ **Listing B.2:** Excerpt from test_1_fma_rd.s.

B. FMA TEST CASES

FMA benchmark program

```
1  /* ... */
2
3  clock_t t_start = clock ();
4
5  // inner loop: several computation
6  for (long j = 0; j < i; j += PARALLEL)
7      {
8
9      /* ... */
10
11     #if defined(BENCHMARK_FMA)
12         c[0] = std::fma (a, b, c[0]);
13     #if PARALLEL > 1
14         c[1] = std::fma (a, b, c[1]);
15     #endif
16
17     /* ... */
18     #if defined(BENCHMARK_ADD)
19         c[0] += a;
20     #if PARALLEL > 1
21         c[1] += a;
22     #endif
23
24     /* ... */
25     #if defined(BENCHMARK_MULT)
26         c[0] *= a;
27     #if PARALLEL > 1
28         c[1] *= a;
29     #endif
30
31     /* ... */
```

C. FMA BENCHMARK PROGRAM

```
32 }
33
34 /* ... */
35
36     clock_t t_end = clock ();
37
38 /* ... */
```

■ **Listing C.1:** Excerpt from benchmark_fma.cpp.

```
1 .L10:
2     incq     %rdx             # j
3     vfmadd231sd %xmm2, %xmm3, %xmm1 # b, a, c$
4     cmpq     %rbx, %rdx      # i, j
5     jl      .L10             #,
```

■ **Listing C.2:** Excerpt from benchmark_fma_1.s.

```
1 .L10:
2     incq   %rdx             # j
3     vaddsd %xmm2, %xmm1, %xmm1 # a, c$, c$
4     cmpq   %rbx, %rdx      # i, j
5     jl    .L10             #,
```

■ **Listing C.3:** Excerpt from benchmark_add_1.s.

```
1 .L10:
2     incq   %rdx             # j
3     vmulsd %xmm2, %xmm1, %xmm1 # a, c$, c$
4     cmpq   %rbx, %rdx      # i, j
5     jl    .L10             #,
```

■ **Listing C.4:** Excerpt from benchmark_mult_1.s.

```
1 .L10:
2     addq   $4, %rdx         #, j
3     vfmadd231sd %xmm1, %xmm2, %xmm3 # b, a, c$0
4     cmpq   %rbx, %rdx      # i, j
5     vfmadd231sd %xmm1, %xmm2, %xmm4 # b, a, c$1
6     vfmadd231sd %xmm1, %xmm2, %xmm5 # b, a, c$2
7     vfmadd231sd %xmm1, %xmm2, %xmm0 # b, a, c$3
8     jl    .L10             #,
```

■ **Listing C.5:** Excerpt from benchmark_fma_4.s.

Bucket visualizations

This appendix is intended to give a visual impression of the bucket alignment and the accumulation process. Therefore each figure contains an orange number line, that indicates for each column the bit significance as a power of two and as a biased exponent representation according to the binary64 format. The accumulation buckets are visualized as 53 bit arrays, labelled a , with two white leading bits, a green accumulation reserve $part_1$, two white *guard* bits, a red *shift* and finally a blue $part_3$, see Chapter 4.2. Each bucket is aligned to the orange number line with a *shift* of 18 bits. For exceptional buckets in the over- and underflow-range the colors have the same meaning, as for "normal" buckets, only $Acc[113]$ in Figure D.2 is initialized with NaN and thus colorless.

Figures D.1 and D.2 show how the utmost buckets differ from the "normal" ones in the inner exponent range. These figures are intended to help with understanding the limitations of BucketSum.

Figure D.3 shows the worst case summation example for the buckets $Acc[56]$ and $Acc[54]$ when using *roundToNearest*. The worst case addend here is $2^2 + 2^{-32}$, which is exactly the tie value of this rounding mode and the only value, that results in an error of magnitude 2^{-32} in this case. This accumulation error of bucket $Acc[56]$ is visualized as red 53 bit array and shows the necessity of the *guard* bits.

Figure D.4 shows the same scenario for *roundTowardNegative* and its worst case addend $2^2 + 2^{-31} - 2^{-50}$. The maximal possible error for this rounding mode is almost twice of that one from *roundToNearest*. The necessity of the *guard* bits becomes clear as well.

Figure D.1.: Visualization of the bucket alignment in the underflow range.

D. BUCKET VISUALIZATIONS

Figure D.4.: Visualization of the stress test case for *roundTowardNegative*.

CD content

- Selected referenced papers
- Software
 - ◆ Benchmarks
 - ▶ **Algorithms** - Implementations of the algorithms of the Chapters 4 and 5. Including *BucketSum*, *BucketDotProd* and the benchmark program.
 - ▶ **Binary64ExponentExtraction** - The software for the benchmark of Chapter 2.3.
 - ▶ **Fma** - The software for the benchmark of Chapter 3.4.
 - ◆ Tests
 - ▶ **BucketInnerProductWorstCases** - Test program for the worst case inner product accumulation scenario.
 - ▶ **BucketSummationWorstCases** - Test program for the worst case summation scenario.
 - ▶ **FmaRounding** - Test program for FMA.
 - ▶ **SystemProperties** - Test program to acquire very specific system properties related to floating-point operations.
 - ◆ README.txt

E. CD CONTENT

- **LaTeX** - The \LaTeX sources of this Master's Thesis.
- `thesis.pdf` - A digital version of this Master's Thesis.